

THE EFFECTS OF MECHANICAL DEFORMATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES EMBEDDED WITH POLYMER BATTERIES

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Abstract

Structural composites embedded with energy cells that synchronously carry load and store electric energy will transform future vehicles. They can replace inert structural components and simultaneously provide supplementary power for light load applications. Rechargeable lithium polymer battery cells are embedded into carbon fibre/epoxy matrix composite laminates, which were then subjected to tensile, flexural and compressive loading to investigate the mechanical and electrical performances of structural batteries. The experimental results show that the integration of battery cells into composite laminates has negligible impact on the mechanical strengths of the composite structures. Furthermore, the battery cells remain 95% effective at loads up to about 50% of the ultimate tensile failure load and 60% of the ultimate flexural failure load.

2 Introduction

The main objective of multifunctional system is to improve the performance of entire system by integrating physical properties of the subsystem constituents[1]. Multifunctional materials and structures have the capability to perform one or more functions sequentially in time or simultaneously[2,3]. In the case of energy storage systems, traditional electrochemical batteries are heavy, bulky, and concentrated (in terms of spatial location for vehicles), which can adversely affect the driving range, space shortage, and dynamic handling of the vehicle. Structural batteries that can carry both mechanical loads and store electric energy may enable significant weight reductions of structural systems, with improved redundancy and performance[4-6]. Recently lithium polymer battery

cells are increasingly used in diverse applications such as unmanned air vehicles (UAVs), unmanned underwater vehicles (UUVs) and electric cars[7,8].

Recently research efforts have been made to embed thin battery cells within composite structures, creating structural battery composites (SBC) that concurrently perform energy storage and structural functions under light mechanical loading. Thomas et al [9-12] embedded thin polymer battery cells into a fibre composite sandwich structure and examined the flexural response and Ragone curves (energy density vs. power density, and specific energy vs. specific power) to characterise the structural and electrical properties of the multifunctional structural power component. Their work demonstrated the feasibility of integrating lithium-ion cells into structural composites to provide energy storage capability (50 Wh/L) without degrading structural performance and buoyancy which was specifically targeted at marine applications. Pereira et al[13] embedded thin film all-solid-state lithium-ion energy cells (100 μm thick) into carbon-fibre-reinforced plastics (CFRP) composites, which withstood both the temperature and pressure required for autoclave manufacture at 120°C. They found that the maximum tensile load that can be applied without degrading the performance of the embedded energy cells was approximately 50% of the tensile strength of the CFRP. Batteries can account for 20-40% of the total UAV weight[14].

2 Materials & Methodology

2.1 Materials

Sigmatex™ carbon 2/2 twill weave fabric (T300, 3 K Tow, 199 GSM) were used to reinforce West

system epoxy 105 cured with slow hardener 206, forming the face sheet of the structure battery composite. Kokam USA rechargeable lithium polymer cells (type SLPB 356495; 95.5 mm × 64.5 mm × 3.7 mm) were used for energy storage, which have an operation temperature range of -20 °C to 60 °C. The charging and discharging mode was conducted by constant current (CC) and constant voltage (CV). The minimum voltage of the battery cells is 3 V, the nominal voltage is 3.7 V and the maximum charging voltage is 4.2 V. The energy cells have maximum charge and discharge current of 4.2 A. The experimental set-up for electrical measurements is shown in Fig. 1. energy storage capacity of 2100 mAh, and weight of 44 g with packaging. Corecell A80 plain SAN closed-cell foam was employed as the core surrounding the polymer battery cells. The battery cells and the foam are bonded to the composite face sheets using Araldite 420 A/B adhesive. Isolated electric wires with long 30mm and thickness 3mm were soldered to the electrodes of the batteries. Composite sandwich specimens, with and without battery cells, were manufactured by the wet lay-up technique and cured at room temperature for 24 hours. The composite face sheet consisted of four composite plies. One battery cell was embedded in the middle of the sandwich specimen through adhesive bonding with both the polymer foam and composite face sheets.

2.2 Methodology

Both the control sandwich specimens (without batteries) and the composite batteries were tested under tension and three-point bending accordance with ASTM standards D3039-7 [15] and D790 [16]. The compression test was done by using anti-buckling guides fixture. The specimen dimensions were 380.0 mm × 64.5 mm × 6.5 mm for tensile tests, 195.5 mm × 64.5 mm × 6.5 mm for flexural tests, and 95.5 mm × 64.5 mm × 6.5 mm for compression tests. The span length of three-point-bending tests was 100 mm.

The control sandwich specimens were first tested to determine their ultimate failure loads under tension, compression and bending. The lithium polymer batteries were charged and discharged by the Cellpro PowerLab 6 multi-chemistry battery workstation to determine the baseline electrical performance in the absence of any mechanical deformation. Parameters such as voltage, current,

internal resistance and energy storage capacity were measured.

Composite batteries were subjected to tension and compression at a load increment of around 25% of the ultimate failure loads of the control specimens. For bending tests, the load increment was 20% of the ultimate flexural strength of the control sandwich specimen under bending. A crosshead speed of 1 mm/min was employed for all three modes of loading. After each loading step, the specimens were unloaded, and charging and discharging were carried out to quantify the electrical performance of the structural battery composites.

3 Results and discussion

In comparison with the mono-functional composite specimens, the multi-functional composite specimens achieved the same maximum strength. Therefore the integration of battery cells and the electrical wires did not cause any noticeable reduction in mechanical performance. The average tensile failure load was 52 kN for both control and SBC specimens as shown in fig 2 (a). The average bending failure load was 1373 kN for control specimen and was 1353 kN for specimens with battery cells as shown in fig 2(b),

Under compression, the foam-core sandwich specimens reached an average strength of 30 kN, by comparison, the composite battery specimens reached only half of the ultimate compressive strength of the control specimens, the average failure load was 17 kN as shown in fig 2 (c). The reason for much lower compressive strength, as compared to the control specimens under compression, is that the composite face-sheets over the battery region were not fully supported against buckling. The battery cells consisted of seventeen folded layers and these layers were not mechanically connected. Under compressive loading, the face-sheets over the region of the battery cell would behave as two separate laminates, without the support of a bonded core. Consequently the laminate would buckle under compression.

Since tensile loading was applied to the SBC specimens at an increment of around 25% of the ultimate failure load of the control, these specimens were subjected to gradually increasing tensile loads of 12 kN, 25 kN, 37 kN and 48 kN. After each load increment, the specimens were unloaded to measure the electrical performance by charging and discharging the embedded battery cells. Under

bending load, the SBC specimens were subjected to gradually increasing flexural loads of 20% of the ultimate bending strength of the control specimens. Therefore, the battery performance was characterised after flexural loads reached 274 N, 548 N, 822 N, 1230 N and 1356 N, respectively. In the case of compressive loading, a load increment of around 25% of the control specimens' compression strength was employed. Due to premature buckling failure under compression, the electric performance of SBC specimens were characterised after subjecting to two load levels: 7.5 kN and 15 kN.

Fig. 3 presents typical images of the fractured specimens under tensile, bending and compressive loading, respectively. The tensile specimens fractured outside the region where the battery cell was embedded, while the bending specimens failed in the middle of the specimen (and the battery cell), near the location of the top roller.

Figure 4-6 show the charging and discharging current versus time for stand-alone battery and structural battery subjected to tensile, bending and compressive loads. The pertinent voltage variations are presented in Figure 7. It is seen that that the application of mechanical loads has reduced the charging and discharging time, indicating a reduction in capacity. In particular, the application of tensile loading of 12 kN, 24 kN, 37 kN and 48 kN on SBC specimens decreased the average time for charging from 54.1 min to 51 min, 50.5 min, 49.2 min and finally to 46.1 min. Similarly, the average time for discharging dropped from 40.1 min to 38.1 min, 37 min, 35.1 min and finally to 33 min, respectively. Under bending, the average charge time decreased from the baseline measurement of 54 min to 53 min, 52.3 min, 52 min, 50 min and finally to 49.1 min, while the average discharge time reduced from 40 min to 39min, 38.5 min, 38min, 37 min, 35.2 min and finally to 35 min, when specimens were subjected to loads at an increment of 20% of the ultimate bending strength.

When the composite battery specimens were loaded at an increment of 25% of the compression failure load, the average charge time decreased from the control condition of 54.03 min to 51.8 min and finally to 50 min, while the average discharge time reduced from 40 min to 39 min and finally to 37 min.

Figure 8 presents the changes in the charging and discharging time after structural batteries were subjected to three different modes of loading.

Figure 9 shows the effect of mechanical loading on the average charging and discharging capacity of the embedded battery cells. Although all three types of mechanical loading caused some reduction in capacity, the tensile loading, for a given percentage of the failure load, seems to cause the most reduction. The average charging capacity decreased from 2100 mAh to 2055mAh at 25% of tensile failure load, then to 1933 mAh at 75% of tensile failure load, and finally to 1881 mAh at 100% tensile failure load. The average discharging capacity for the same battery decreased from the baseline value of 2086 mAh to 1856 mAh when subjected to 100% the tensile failure load. Nevertheless, the total reduction in capacity of SBC specimens was only approximately 10 %. The average values and standard of errors for the changes of the internal resistance (ΔR) with the applied loads are plotted in Figure 10. Firstly, the internal resistance was unchanged after soldering the wires. As the mechanical loading increased, the average internal resistance of SBC specimens increased gradually. At a given percentage of the failure loads, tensile loading produced the largest change in internal resistance, from 11.1 m Ω , to 13 m Ω , 13.5 m Ω , 14.7 m Ω and finally to 18 m Ω at 100% failure load.

In general, the embedded battery cells could be charged and discharged upon the application of the mechanical loads, even after the complete failure of the composites. The change in energy storage capacity was less than 5% after 60% of bending failure load and 50% of tensile and compressive failure loads were applied. After the application of higher mechanical loads, greater degradation in electrical performance occurred, especially in the case of tensile loading. Loading the composite batteries to 100% the bending strength reduced the charging and discharging time of the battery by 5 min from the baseline performance. Greater reduction in the energy storage capacity was observed for tensile tests than that pertinent to bending tests, which was accompanied by a greater increase in the internal resistance under tensile loading than the other two loading modes. Since the embedded battery was able to maintain the maximum energy storage capacity during mechanical loads, i.e. the time for charging and discharging did not change significantly after the SBC specimens were subjected to different mechanical loads, they are considered as close to fully functional.

Fig.11 shows the correlation between the percentage of changes in battery's capacity ($\Delta C/C_0$) and in the internal resistance ($\Delta R/R_0$) after being subjected to tension, bending and compressive loading. It is interesting to note that the reduction in battery's charging and discharging capacity, after being subjected to tensile, bending and compressive deformation, correlates well with the changes in the internal resistance. Consequently, resistance may be used a good indicator for detecting degradation in a battery's performance. The precise mechanisms responsible for the observed increase in internal resistance and reduction in energy capacity of the structural batteries remain unclear, mainly due to the complexity of the system and the many contributing factors. Recent studies have identified that one possible cause is the viscoelastic creep of the porous separator in lithium-ion batteries[17]. Changes in the pore structure, in particular, the pore closure, may reduce the efficiency of ion transport, increasing the internal resistance and reducing capacity.

6. Conclusion

The performance of multifunctional structure that made of embedding a lithium polymer batteries in a composite structures has been investigated by subjecting them to various mechanical loadings .the electric performance was evaluated for the energy cells by cycles of charging and discharging. Three different mechanical loadings were investigated, including tension, compression and bending. The results showed that embedding lithium polymer batteries into composite sandwich structure did not significantly alter the mechanical properties under tensile and flexural loading, but caused premature buckling failure as compared to sandwich structures without battery cells. Degradations in batteries charging and discharging capacity have been found to correlate strongly with the increase in the internal electrical resistance.

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'Figure. 1. Experimental set-up for electrical performance measurements'

Fig. 2. Load displacement curves for both uni-functional composite and structural battery composite under mechanical loading. (a) tensile (b) three-point-bending and (c) compressive loading'.

‘Fig. 3. Photos of fractured composite sandwich panels and composite batteries (indicated by copper wires) subjected to tensile, flexural and compressive loading’.

'Fig. 4. a) Charging and b) discharging current as a function of time before and after applying tensile loads'.

'Fig. 5. a) Charging and b) discharging current as a function of time before and after applying bending loads'.

'Fig. 6. a) Charging and b) discharging current as a function of time before and after applying compressive loads'.

'Fig. 7. Charging and discharging voltage before and after applying a) tensile; b) flexural and c) compressive loading'.

‘Fig. 8. The average time of charging and discharging affected by mechanical loading’.

‘Fig. 9. Capacity of the battery cells affected by mechanical loading’.

‘Fig. 10. Internal resistance of battery cells affected by mechanical loading’.

‘Fig. 11. The percentage of capacity reduction versus the percentage of internal resistance increase after tensile, bending and compressive loading’.